

Synthesis and Preliminary Antibacterial Activity of 3-(2-Arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-4-hydroxy- 4'-Substituted Sulphamoyl Azobenzenes

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In view of expected antibacterial action, compounds related to the title compounds were synthesised through the reaction of 2-arylamino-5-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles with 4-substituted sulphamoyl phenyl diazonium salts, obtained by diazotization of some sulphonamides. The starting 2,5-disubstituted thiadiazoles were prepared by cyclization of 1-salicyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazides by two procedures.

Ir spectral data and preliminary antibacterial screening against four micro organisms are presented.

ANTIBACTERIAL action is an inherent property of some chemical moieties. The derivatives of 1,3,4-thiadiazoles were reported as effective antibacterial or antifungal agents e.g., 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles with amino, arylamino, aryl and aryloxymethyl groups¹⁻⁴. Besides, substituted thiadiazoles have been proved to be more antifungal than the related oxadiazoles or pyrazoles⁴. Conversely, 2-(4-pyridyl)-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were found to be ineffective as antitubercular agents⁵.

2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were synthesised by acid cyclization of 1,4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides, another chemical moiety referred to as being antibacterial⁶⁻⁹.

The replacement of the basic N⁴-amino group of sulphonamides by such groups as acylamino, azo or hydrazo still effects bacteriostatic action^{10,11} due to *in vivo* release of the parent sulphonamide by metabolic processes.

The present communication attempts to prepare effective antibacterial agents having substituted thiadiazole nucleus surmounted on 4-hydroxy-4'-substituted sulphamoylazobenzene molecules.

Discussion

For preparation of the final compounds, the following sequence of reactions was followed. Salicylic hydrazide (I)¹² was condensed with arylisothiocyanates¹³ to yield 1-salicyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazides (II-XI)¹⁴⁻¹⁶ which in turn were cyclized at room temperature to 2,5-disubstituted thiadiazoles (XII-XXI) using concentrated sulphuric acid^{17,18}. The same cyclization was also possible either by warming the starting thiosemicarbazides with conc. sulphuric acid or by refluxing in a mixture of

absolute ethanol and conc. sulphuric acid (3 : 1). Finally, the prepared 2-arylamino-5-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (XII-XXI) were dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and treated with cold diazotized sulphonamide solutions to yield the final azo-dyes (XXII-XXXI), as shown in Scheme 1.

Compd. no.	R	R'
II, XII	C ₆ H ₅	H
III, XIII	4(OH)C ₆ H ₄	Pyrimidin-2-yl
IV, XIV	4(Br)C ₆ H ₄	Thiazol-2-yl
V, XV	4(MeO)C ₆ H ₄	4-Me-pyrimidin-2-yl
VI, XVI	4(EtO)C ₆ H ₄	5-Me-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl
VII, XVII	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	4,6-Di(Me)pyrimidin-2-yl
VIII, XVIII	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	5-MeO-pyrimidin-2-yl
IX, XIX	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	5-MeO-pyrimidin-2-yl
X, XX	2,5-Di(Me)C ₆ H ₃	Thiazol-2-yl
XI, XXI	3,5-Di(Me)C ₆ H ₃	H
XXII	C ₆ H ₅	H
XXIII	4(OH)C ₆ H ₄	Pyrimidin-2-yl
XXIV	4(Br)C ₆ H ₄	Thiazol-2-yl
XXV	4(MeO)C ₆ H ₄	4-Me-pyrimidin-2-yl
XXVI	4(EtO)C ₆ H ₄	5-Me-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl
XXVII	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	4,6-Di(Me)pyrimidin-2-yl
XXVIII	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	5-MeO-pyrimidin-2-yl
XXIX	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	5-MeO-pyrimidin-2-yl
XXX	2,5-Di(Me)C ₆ H ₃	Thiazol-2-yl
XXXI	3,5-Di(Me)C ₆ H ₃	H

Scheme 1

The thiosemicarbazides (II-XI) have bands¹⁴⁻¹⁶ at 1650 (CO stretch chelated with OH), 3320 cm⁻¹ (OH stretch chelated with CO), broad band at 3250-3000 (NH stretch) and at 1100 cm⁻¹ (CS stretch). These bands have disappeared in the cyclized products and the NH absorption was recorded at 3250 cm⁻¹ besides the OH stretching at 3400 cm⁻¹. The prepared azo compounds XXII-XXXI have shown the N=N stretching at 1620-1625 cm⁻¹ and the SO₂ stretching as two bands at 1310 and 1150 cm⁻¹.

Antibacterial screening: Preliminary antibacterial screening was performed by the cup-plate diffusion method against *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* using solutions of the tested compounds in propylene glycol (1 mg ml⁻¹). Results obtained are summarized in Table 4 including comparison with the starting thiosemicarbazides and the four sulphadiazole drugs. Most of the compounds have shown better results than the reference samples.

Experimental

Melting points were uncorrected and determined in open capillaries using the Gallenkamp melting point apparatus. IR spectra were run using a nujol mull in Beckman IR 4210 spectrophotometer.

1-Salicyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazides (II-XI)¹⁴⁻¹⁶: A solution of the appropriate arylisothiocyanate (0.04 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was gradually added with stirring to a solution of salicylic hydrazide (0.04 mol, 6.08 g) in ethanol (60 ml), and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. During reflux some derivatives crystallized out while the others required the reaction mixture to be concentrated to half its volume and cooled. Crude products were filtered and crystallized from ethanol as shiny white needles. The compounds prepared by this procedure are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—1-SALICYL-4-ARYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDES

Compd. no.	Yield %	m.p.* °C
II	74	188 (190)
III	98	206 (206)
IV	75	242 (246)
V	82	212 (214)
VI	87	210 (215)
VII	98	216 (218)
VIII	97	175 (177)
IX	95	185 (186)
X	98	170†
XI	95	179‡

* Reported values in parenthesis. Analysis, N% ; Found/(Calcd.) : † 13.10 (13.33), ‡ 13.40 (13.33).

2-Arylamino-5-(o-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (XII-XXI): Method A. Appropriate 1,4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazide (II-XI) (1.2 g) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (12 ml) and treated with conc. sulphuric acid (4 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min and refluxed on water bath for 30 min. The deep yellow mixture was cooled and then gradually poured in equal volume of ice cooled water. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water until free from acid, dried in air and the product crystallized from ethanol.

Method B. Appropriate 1,4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazide (1 g) was mixed with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 90 min or warmed on water bath for 5 min. The deep yellow viscous reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice (30 g) and the precipitate obtained was treated as above. The data for the products are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2—2-ARYLAMINO-5-(O-HYDROXYPHENYL)-1,3,4-THIAZOLE

Compd. no.	Yield %		m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.) N
	A	B		
XII	87	80	137	15.50 (15.61)
XIII	88	95	153	13.50 (13.89)
XIV	82	89	176	12.20 (12.07)
XV	72	85	153	14.00 (14.04)
XVI	79	55	132	13.30 (13.41)
XVII	85	74	141	14.70 (14.88)
XVIII	98	75	158	14.90 (14.88)
XIX	65	60	145	14.60 (14.88)
XX	87	70	134	14.00 (14.18)
XXI	85	65	146	13.90 (14.18)

3-(2-Arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-4-hydroxy-4'-substituted sulphamoylazobenzenes (XXII-XXXI): Appropriate sulphonamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in HCl (1 : 1, 30 ml) and cooled to 0-5°. Cold sodium nitrite solution (20%, 10 ml) was gradually added with stirring keeping the temperature below 5°. The so diazotized sulphonamide solution was added with stirring to a cold solution of the selected thiadiazole (XII-XXI) (0.01 mol) in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 40 ml) below 5°. The resulted reddish orange reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h and the precipitate formed was filtered and washed with water till neutral. Products were air dried and crystallized from ethanol as reddish orange crystals. The data for the prepared azo-dyes are listed in Table 3.

Preliminary antibacterial screening: Solutions of the tested compounds were prepared in propylene

TABLE 3—8-(2-ARYLAMINO-1,3,4-THIAZOL-5-YL)-4-HYDROXY-4'-SUBSTITUTED SULPHAMOYLAZOBENZENES

Compd. no.	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)
XXII	96	139	18.40 (18.58)
XXIII	84	132	19.70 (19.83)
XXIV	82	160	16.20 (15.96)
XXV	83	145	19.45 (19.51)
XXVI	79	138	18.60 (18.86)
XXVII	91	165	19.35 (19.58)
XXVIII	93	135	19.30 (19.51)
XXIX	75	139	19.60 (19.51)
XXX	60	140	17.50 (17.41)
XXXI	62	131	17.70 (17.50)

TABLE 4—ANTIBACTERIAL SCREENING

Compd. no.	Inhibition zones, mm			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. Sub.</i>	<i>P. aer.</i>	<i>S. aur.</i>
II	19	18	10	21
III	20	20	23	25
IV	18	9	9	20
V	12	9	10	20
VI	—	12	12	23
VII	16	17	20	22
VIII	18	13	12	24
IX	18	20	18	25
X	12	15	—	24
XI	21	20	18	24
XII	11	11	15	23
XIII	12	18	18	25
XIV	15	21	21	20
XV	11	—	12	22
XVI	11	18	15	20
XVII	9	12	10	20
XVIII	10	13	11	19
XIX	15	12	9	20
XX	12	10	14	21
XXI	13	12	12	22
XXII	12	11	9	15
XXIII	13	12	16	20
XXIV	11	15	16	18
XXV	14	13	9	18
XXVI	12	—	15	15
XXVII	10	9	20	15
XXVIII	9	12	12	18
XXIX	11	13	14	15
XXX	11	10	22	19
XXXI	12	13	16	21
A	13	11	20	16
B	15	10	15	18
C	11	12	12	19
D	10	10	20	16
E	—	—	—	—

A=Sulphanilamide, B=Sulphadiazine, C=Sulphamerazine, D=Sulphamethizole, E=Propylene glycol.

glycol (1 mg ml⁻¹). The bacterial cultures were grown on nutrient agar ; 24 h grown cultures of *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* and a 14 day grown culture of *B. subtilis*¹⁹ were used.

Nutrient agar was sterilized at 121° for 15 min and allowed to cool to 50°. 1 ml of the appropriate culture of the test organism was added to each 100 ml medium. Ingredients were thoroughly mixed and poured into petri dishes (15 cm) containing 50 ml seeded medium each. After setting, cups of 8 mm dia. were cut and each received about six drops of the test solutions. Petri dishes were then incubated for 24 h at 37° and the resulted inhibition zones were measured (Table 4).

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